

BioINSouth

Supporting regional environmental sustainability assessment for the BIO-based sectors to improve INnovation, INdustries and INclusivity in SOUTH Europe

Deliverable 3.2 HUB Guidelines Final

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BioINSouth

Supporting regional environmental sustainability assessment for the BIO-based sectors to improve INnovation, INdustries and INclusivity in SOUTH Europe

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Abbreviations	
ACIS	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia
ART	Agriculture Research Ltd.
EFI	European Forest Institute
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ESF	European Social Fund
GA	Grant Agreement
KoM	Kick-Off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MARG	Multi- Actor Regional Groups
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
PNO	PNO Innovation Single Member Private Company
SME	Small- Medium Enterprise
TTK	Termesztudományi Kutatóközpont
WP	Work Package
WPC	Work Package of Communication

Executive Summary

This deliverable (D3.2) **represents the final version of the BioINSouth HUB guidelines, building on the foundations laid in D3.1.** It integrates real-world insights from the initial establishment of the HUBs, their kick-off meetings, and the early-stage stakeholder engagements across the BioINSouth Mediterranean regions. The guidelines provide BioINSouth HUB Coordinators with practical tools and peer-reviewed methodologies—proven in BIOEASTsUP and RuralBioUp—for managing HUB governance, fostering stakeholder co-creation, and communicating HUB value. **They offer concrete recommendations to inspire, engage and mobilize enterprises, research bodies, civil society and public administrations into active, long-term participants in the regional bioeconomy ecosystem.** The document also includes three key annexes: a mandatory action plan template (Annex 1), a draft for the regional co-creation workshops (Annex 2), and a communication guide to help HUBs attract and retain stakeholders (Annex 3).

Introduction

As part of the BioINSouth project's mission to catalyse sustainable, inclusive bioeconomy strategies in Southern Europe, **D3.2 delivers final guidance to support the effective operation of regional BioINSouth HUBs. These HUBs serve as multi-actor platforms that gather and align stakeholders around regional bioeconomy objectives.** D3.2 builds upon the initial framework of D3.1, now enriched by feedback from MARG (Multi-Actor Regional Group) interactions and the first phase of activities related to the HUBs' establishment. It reflects both common principles and the diverse realities across participating regions. Crucially, this document introduces the peer review methodology—assessed in BIOEASTsUP and RuralBioUp—as a tool to enable experience exchange, mutual learning, and continuous improvement among HUB coordinators. Governance model recommendations, co-creation techniques, and strategic communication tips are provided to ensure HUBs can function as long-term enablers of innovation and transformation within their territories.

1 Methodology

This deliverable (D3.2) **represents the final version of the BioINSouth HUB Guidelines and builds upon the foundation laid in D3.1.** Following the submission of D3.1 “HUB Guidelines,” all BioINSouth HUB Coordinators were invited to a collective HUB Coordinators’ Meeting on 7 February 2025 to discuss both completed and ongoing steps towards HUB establishment. During this meeting, the contents of **D3.1 were reviewed with the HUB Coordinators, focusing on identifying any additional information that could better support the establishment of BioINSouth HUBs.** BIOEAST HUB CR encouraged the Coordinators to reflect on the content and highlight any further needs to ensure the guidelines would serve as a practical and supportive tool. As a result, D3.2 “HUB Guidelines – Final” integrates this feedback and includes several key updates: a shorter, **more practical version** of D3.1 (distributed in March and included in Annex 4), new content on the **governance** of BioINSouth HUBs as entities (provided in Chapter 2), and a presentation of the **peer review methodology** developed under the BIOEASTsUP Project (the methodology is described in Chapter 3).

In alignment with the Description of Action (DoA), BIOEAST HUB CR aimed for this deliverable to be as practical and actionable as possible, serving as both a guidance tool and a source of inspiration for other regions considering HUB establishment. **Therefore, as foreseen in the DoA, this document also aims to capture practical insights primarily from stakeholder engagement activities, which are key to successful HUB establishment** (the reporting and monitoring procedures is described in Chapter 4, the results in Chapter 5).

The next key milestone for the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators will be the realization of the HUB KoMs, to be held in July 2025, and development of individual Action Plans for each BioINSouth HUB. These plans will outline concrete steps, objectives, and activities tailored to the specific regional contexts of each BioINSouth HUB. Importantly, each Action Plan will be validated in collaboration with HUB Members during co-creation workshops, which will take place as part of the BioINSouth HUB Kick-Off Meetings in July 2025, and will be integrated as Annexes in the future D3.3. **Recognising the complexity of this task, the BIOEAST HUB CR has proactively provided support materials to assist Coordinators in drafting their Action Plans and preparing for the validation workshops.** Methodological guidance and recommended steps for Action Plan development are available in Annex 1. In addition, Annex 2 offers practical suggestions for the design and facilitation of the co-creation validation workshops.

2 BioINSouth HUB Governance

Despite the common objectives and goals of the various HUBs in the BioINSouth project, it is expected to face substantial variations into their operational mode, due to the differences between them on regional and sectoral level. The aim is to reach a smooth implementation into the operational mode, therefore suggestions for a certain governance is mandatory. Considering the differences mentioned above it is not feasible to have a common governance model for all HUBs. Therefore, we will define some mandatory principles to be adopted by all HUBs independently which model they will adopt, and then to provide suggestions on how to adapt the modus operandi on a case-by-case basis.

It is important to keep in mind that the basic role of the HUBs as it is also described in the guidance document, is to act as multi-actor platforms that promote the co-creation of disruptive tools and innovative solutions as they ensure that the transition to a bio-based economy is inclusive involving various stakeholders and implementing strategies that align with the sustainability goals.

2.1 Governance Principles

Several “must” factors must be considered before establishing any governance model:

- **Transparency:** open decision-making processes, clear communication, and consideration of the opinion of all stakeholders independently of their “specific weight” in the HUB.
- **Inclusiveness:** engaging a wide range of actors, including marginalized groups (when this is relevant), Indigenous people, SMEs, and youth.
- **Flexibility:** adaptive structures that can respond to emerging scientific, technological, and market developments.
- **Sustainability:** ensuring environmental, economic, and social sustainability in all activities and initiatives.
- **Integrity and Ethics:** upholding scientific integrity, ethical resource use, and fair benefit-sharing.

2.2 Organizational Structures

The responsible person for the operation of the HUB preferably should be the respective BioINSouth partner. This person will be in charge of the overall governance and the reporting to the project. Further on the following structures can also be considered (not necessarily all in each HUB):

- **Governing Board:** a body composed of representatives from key stakeholder groups (academia, industry, government, civil society) and responsible for a strategic leadership in cooperation with the HUB coordinator.
- **Advisory Panels:** expert groups offering specialized knowledge in areas like biotechnology, policy, sustainability, and Indigenous knowledge systems. The MARG, already established at a regional level, could potentially serve as an Advisory Panel.
- **Management Team:** operational body responsible for day-to-day activities, reporting to the Governing Board.
- **Thematic Working Groups:** Focused units tackling specific areas like bioproduct development, regulatory frameworks, education and skills, etc.

2.3 Key Governance Mechanisms

This is the focus of the HUB operation.

- **Stakeholder Engagement Framework:** processes for consultation, co-creation, and feedback loops with diverse actors.
- **Performance Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E):** setting KPIs, periodic reporting, and impact assessments.
- **Risk Management:** identifying risks (technical, financial, political) and creating mitigation strategies.
- **Conflict Resolution Mechanisms:** establishing neutral platforms for mediation and dispute resolution.
- **Knowledge Management:** systems to capture, store, and share knowledge produced within the Hub.

2.4 Policy Alignment and Advocacy

It is important that the HUB provides a Policy Coherence, ensuring that its activities align with national, regional, and international Bioeconomy strategies. Also, to take Advocacy Initiatives by promoting supportive policies and regulatory frameworks.

2.5 Financial Sustainability

In order to guarantee its operational capacity, the HUB should consider Diverse Funding Streams: Public funding, private investment, grants, membership fees and service contracts can be some options. Needless to underline that transparent budgeting, auditing, and financial reporting practices are mandatory.

2.6 Regional and Global Collaboration

Partnerships with other Bioeconomy Hubs, universities, related organizations, and industry groups to share best practices and jointly develop innovations must be included in each HUB's agenda. Additionally, a horizontal cooperation with other HUBs within the BioINSouth project is mandatory.

2.7 Additional and Optional Elements

- Each HUB can consider the inclusion to its governance one or more of the following options:
- Digital Governance: this relates to Data Management (Secure, ethical handling of research data, innovation metrics, and stakeholder information) and to various Digital Collaboration Tools such as platforms for remote collaboration, shared resource management, and innovation tracking.
- Capacity Building & Education: this may include training programs for members on governance best practices, leadership, ethics, and technical skills. Also supporting innovation ecosystems through incubators, accelerators, and mentorship programs.
- Actions related to specific requirements of one or more stakeholders' groups or related to defined regional particularities.

Strong, inclusive, and adaptive governance is critical to the success of the HUB. It enables collaboration, accelerates innovation, fosters trust among stakeholders, and ensures that the Bioeconomy grows in a way that is sustainable, ethical, and beneficial for the society at large.

3 Peer review

The peer review methodology adopted in the BIOEASTsUP project offers a practical, low-threshold tool for mutual learning and exchange among HUB coordinators (BIOEASTsUP, 2021⁴). It centres on a structured but informal evaluation of a selected good practice by peers working in similar roles or contexts. Rather

⁴ Kubáňková, M., & Nedělník, J. (2021). BIOEASTsUP Peer Review Report: Technology Transfer Good Practice Handbook (D2.4, Final Version). Agriculture Research Ltd., BIOEASTsUP Project. Available at: www.bioeast.eu

than following a rigid scientific protocol, the methodology encourages reflective dialogue, constructive feedback, and experience-based learning. **This approach was evaluated through a series of multi-day peer review workshops, which combined presentations, moderated discussions, and expert contributions. It proved particularly effective in generating actionable insights on technology transfer and stakeholder engagement.** The experience also underscored the value of involving innovation brokers, producing accessible outreach materials, and progressively scaling activities from the regional to the national and international levels.

3.1 Peer review methodology

The peer review methodology used in the BIOEASTsUP project is a structured, yet informal learning process that brings together professionals from similar fields—such as HUB coordinators, researchers, and policymakers—to evaluate and exchange experiences around a selected good practice. It is not an audit or scientific evaluation, but a mutual learning exercise aimed at improving real-world implementation.

The process involves:

- Selection of a good practice by a host organisation (e.g. technology transfer or stakeholder engagement).
- Multi-day online or in-person sessions, featuring presentations, expert inputs, and open discussion.
- Reflection and feedback from peer reviewers, who analyse strengths, challenges, and opportunities for transferability.
- Documentation of results to feed into strategic improvement and cross-regional inspiration.
- This method encourages honest dialogue, builds trust, and supports capacity-building across regions. It has proven especially useful for enhancing technology transfer systems and bioeconomy uptake through stakeholder-informed improvement.

3.2 Peer review good practice to inspire

An example of good practice was the Technology Transfer Centre at the Agriculture Research Ltd. (ART) in the Czech Republic, established in 2010 by Marie Kubáňková and Jan Nedělník with Jaroslava Hyršlová. After a decade of operation, ART became one of the founding members of the BIOEAST HUB CR. The Technology Transfer Centre successfully bridged research and practice by supporting SMEs in bioeconomy innovation—particularly in agriculture, food systems, and bioenergy—well before the term “bioeconomy” gained national traction in 2018. Its success was rooted in early investments in capacity building and the establishment of a strong stakeholder network—priorities that closely align with the foundational needs of BioINSouth HUBs.

For BioINSouth HUBs, this methodology is not only a learning mechanism but also a governance and community-building tool. It helps HUB coordinators identify transferable practices, build trust through regular peer contact, and co-develop strategies adapted to their unique regional challenges. By implementing this method, BioINSouth HUBs can benefit from shared intelligence, avoid common pitfalls, and strengthen the coherence and sustainability of their regional bioeconomy efforts.

4 Monitoring & Mentoring of the BioINSouth HUBs' Establishment

To better understand the process and challenges of stakeholder engagement, BioINSouth HUB Coordinators were invited to submit a short report summarising their experiences. These reports focused on the obstacles encountered, the feedback received from stakeholders, and the overall dynamics of establishing the HUBs. The collected questionnaire responses are available on the BioINSouth Project SharePoint, while the Reporting Questionnaire Template can be found in Annex 5.

In addition to gathering this valuable feedback, the BIOEAST HUB CR provided direct support by allocating two dedicated sessions, in which each BioINSouth HUB Coordinator was encouraged to share concerns, raise specific issues, and discuss final steps in the HUB establishment process. This peer-exchange format enabled shared learning and collective problem-solving at a critical stage in the project's implementation.

4.1 Communication of the BioINSouth HUBs' activities

In terms of communicating each BioINSouth HUB's activities, the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators are responsible to produce and communicate/ disseminate the materials, through the official website of the project and, in case, also creating LinkedIn account of the HUB or by using the LinkedIn personal accounts of the implementation team.

The key topics of communication will be modified by the BioINSouth Coordinator based on the regional specificities and interests. According to the BioINSouth Project Objectives, such topics could be related to the support of decision makers, regional interests, stakeholder engagement, tools and methodologies and their demonstration and validation, policy recommendations, dissemination and replication, impact, and outcomes, etc.

Reporting of such activities fall under WP7 and can be included in the validation of the relevant KPIs and therefore should be reported through the WP7 established channels to WP7 Leader.

The Communication Strategy of each BioINSouth HUB will be produced by the respective BioINSouth HUB Coordinator, with the support of WP7 Leader PNO and BIOEAST HUB CR, and included in D3.3 "BioINSouth HUB Action Plan." The strategy will take into account the contents of D7.1 "D&C&E Plan."

A set of suggestions for the BioINSouth HUB Communication plan will be created by WP7 Leader PNO, providing suggestions for maximising visibility of the HUBs. There are several co-creation activities, as well as individual activities in HUB level, for which the HUB Coordinators and the respective partners are solely responsible for communicating/disseminating. WP7 Leader PNO will provide assistance to all HUB Coordinators to stylise their posts/texts/presentations.

BioINSouth HUB Coordinators are responsible for publishing their communication/ dissemination materials online in a timely manner taking into account the instructions and suggestions of WP7 Leader PNO.

4.2 Cooperation between the BioINSouth HUBs and support for the BioINSouth Initiative

Following the establishment of the BioINSouth HUBs and their Kick-Off Meetings in July 2025, **it will be essential to maintain regular communication among HUB Coordinators**. This will help ensure operational alignment, facilitate the identification of collaborative opportunities across HUBs, and support the organisation of joint activities.

To this end, will be held a periodic BioINSouth HUB Coordinators' Meetings, starting after the Kick-Off Meetings, under the activities of T3.2 and T3.3. These meetings will offer a platform for Coordinators to report on their recent activities (reporting format to be defined), share experiences, and address both individual and joint topics in progress.

The strategic role of the BioINSouth HUBs within the broader BioINSouth initiative – outlined in Deliverable D3.1 – extends beyond the lifetime of the BioINSouth project. This long-term vision can serve as a strong motivator for HUB members (as demonstrated in Portugal, more details are provided in Chapter 5). During the implementation phase, Coordinators will be guided on how their HUB operations contribute to and support the BioINSouth Initiative. This will be managed in close collaboration between the BIOEAST HUB CR and project Coordinator SPRING, also leading Task 3.2.

4.3 Facilitating cooperation between the BioINSouth and BIOEAST HUBs

The BioINSouth Initiative draws inspiration from the success of the BIOEAST Initiative², launched in 2016 by the Visegrad Group and later joined by seven additional Central and Eastern European (CEE) countries formerly part of the Eastern Bloc. The progress of the BIOEAST Initiative – now fully recognized by the European Commission and regularly consulted in EU strategy development – is largely attributed to the dedicated efforts of Dr. Barna Kovacs, Secretary General of the BIOEAST Initiative. Recent political momentum, supported by the Hungarian EU Presidency³ (June–December 2024) and the current Polish Presidency (January–June 2025), has further amplified the visibility of BIOEAST topics. In parallel, the Boost4BIOEAST project, launched in January 2024, is actively establishing national BIOEAST HUBs to operationalize the BIOEAST Initiative's goals.

As outlined in D3.1, BioINSouth and BIOEAST HUBs share a common purpose: supporting macro-regional bioeconomy initiatives rather than acting as stand-alone hubs established by individual EU-funded projects. Given their shared mission, it is both strategic and natural to encourage coordination and knowledge exchange not only between the BioINSouth and Boost4BIOEAST projects, but also between their respective HUBs.

The first coordination meeting between the Communication Work Package leaders of both projects took place in February 2025, facilitated by the BIOEAST HUB CR team, who proposed a meeting to host a joint co-creation workshop for BioINSouth and BIOEAST HUB Coordinators. The aim was to foster peer-to-peer dialogue, mutual learning, and identification of common priorities and practices.

The idea has received initial support from the European Forest Institute, EFI (supporting BIOEAST HUB establishment) and Termesztudományi Kutatóközpont, TTK–BIOEAST HUB Hungary (coordinating

² www.bioeast.eu

³ We can name the Council [Conclusion](#) following the BIOEAST Stakeholder or BIOEAST [Manifesto](#)

BIOEAST HUB activities). The proposed timeline for the workshop is early 2026, pending further discussions at a more advanced stage of both projects.

5 BioINSouth HUBs' Progress and Results from the Reporting Exercise and Experience on Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement is the cornerstone of successful HUB establishment. As outlined in the Methodology Chapter, a key step in this process was the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators' Meeting held on 7 February 2025. During this meeting, BioINSouth HUB Coordinators provided feedback on Deliverable D3.1 and its supporting documents, and shared progress updates since their individual preparatory meetings and experiences with stakeholders' engagement. **Discussions included experiences with stakeholder mapping and identifying region-specific challenges where further support was needed.** Overall, the Coordinators confirmed the relevance and practical value of the materials provided, reinforcing their alignment with the real-world needs of HUB establishment. The feedback from those discussions were further enhanced by the reporting questionnaire (Annex 5) the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators were asked to complete. The overall insights described by the individual BioINSouth HUBs are described in the following sub- chapters.

5.1 BioINSouth HUB of Andalusia

The BioINSouth HUB of Andalusia is focusing on following the Quadruple Helix approach in stakeholder identification and will pay special attention not only to the region but also into linking their activities to the interests of the BioINSouth Initiative. Their stakeholders were engaged through email communication, with the majority of them being personal contacts of the coordinating organisation. Their eagerness and interest to collaborate with the BioINSouth HUB is palpable, however the MoU acquirement procedure takes time. The main topic of interest is aligning BioINSouth HUB activities with the regional strategies to build regional nodes of activity. The possibility of regional actions affecting the BioINSouth KoM in July 2025 was noted and will be taken into account in planning.

5.2 BioINSouth HUB of Asturias

The BioINSouth HUB of Asturias reported their interest in increasing the engagement of civic society and start-up companies into their members and highlighted the importance of maintaining a uniform schedule of timelines and deadlines for the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators to follow. The HUB Coordinating team presented the BioINSouth Project and HUB in four different meeting, also presenting the opportunities for the BioINSouth HUB Members. The communication with stakeholders was performed both through in person meetings and also emails and phone calls. The prospective Members were identified through contacts made during the MARG formation, also focusing on establishing a solid network with other initiatives of similar objectives that are already implemented in the region. The stakeholders were interested to discuss what their obligations will be to the BioINSouth Project through being members of the HUB, as well as the establishment of communication and collaboration with the other BioINSouth HUBs. Their interests also lie in exploring successfully implemented bioeconomy strategies in biomass exploitation and overcoming legal restrictions to the adaptation of certain circular economy business models. While the stakeholders were very welcoming and supportive of the initiative presented, the deciding factor for many to not sign an MoU was their limited available capacity and their existing involvement to similar activities.

5.3 BioINSouth HUB of Campania

The BioINSouth HUB of Campania highlighted their cooperation with the University of Naples, who will host their HUB's offices in their premises and focus on being in alignment with the regional authorities of Campania. Their stakeholders are highly involved in the research and industry sectors, with their main interests lying in bioeconomy and biorefineries. Most of the stakeholders were personal contacts and others were suggestions made by Regional Institutions. The topics of interest of the stakeholders are in alignment with the BioINSouth objectives, with the stakeholders being incredibly supportive of the initial idea of the BioINSouth Initiative and the potential of the BioINSouth HUB they were invited to.

5.4 BioINSouth HUB of Centro- Region

The BioINSouth HUB of Centro Region will focus on the Quadruple Helix approach with identifying stakeholders and aim to reach and cooperate with more SMEs. The contacted stakeholders were personal contacts or suggested by their MARG members. One of the main topics of interest for the stakeholders was the potential funding of the BioINSouth HUB and its activities in the future and especially after the completion of the BioINSouth Project. A special circumstance is identified by the BioINSouth HUB Coordinator, given that there are no regional authorities in the Portuguese governmental scheme. The regional representation is through bodies that adapt and implement national strategies to the regions but have no authority to change those strategies, an interesting situation that will need to be accounted for in the future of the BioINSouth HUB. Along with the MARG members, the BioINSouth HUB Coordinating partner has identified a number of Working Groups, topics that appear to be the most popular and interesting to the regional stakeholders based on the needs and activities in the region, a fact that will greatly ease the conversation on deciding the BioINSouth HUB's activities.

5.5 BioINSouth HUB of Cyprus

The BioINSouth HUB of Cyprus reported their intent to continue in mapping the regional stakeholders and their intent to focus their activities on capacity building and education, in line with their expertise and active work. The HUB Coordinators are eagerly preparing for the July KoM of their HUB, having already invited thirty-two organisations, since their stakeholders have expressed their preference of written communication for key points but noting that in person or online meetings are better suited for discussions. Many of those stakeholders are personal working connections of the HUB Coordinating partner. While the stakeholders' interests align with those of the BioINSouth Project, their main concern for the BioINSouth HUB was the future funding mechanisms and whether a specific bioeconomy value chain was identified for implementation. Also, due to the extensive experience of similar actions that remain solely to a theoretical level, the stakeholders are apprehensive to join another such initiative and focus on what steps can be taken to not have a similar outcome. All inputs are greatly appreciated and will be instrumental for the decision making of the BioINSouth HUB.

5.6 BioINSouth HUB of Nouvelle- Aquitaine

The BioINSouth HUB of Nouvelle- Aquitaine engaged their stakeholders through online communication, both written and through online meetings. The stakeholders were identified both through their public presence in the region and through personal contacts of the HUB Coordinating partner. The stakeholders were highly interested in the BioINSouth Project objectives and Initiative, while being curious with regards

to the level of commitment the signed MoU provides and what their responsibilities are as Members of the BioINSouth HUB. The BioINSouth HUB Coordinator has started discussing preparations for the July Kick-Off Meeting of the HUB.

5.7 BioINSouth HUB of the Peloponnese

The BioINSouth HUB of the Peloponnese recognised that the status quo of bioeconomy education is inadequate compared to its importance and plans to focus on the sectors of energy and food for their individual activities. They have noted that the education around bioeconomy is scarce and poorly organised, achieved through teachings of bioeconomy aspects as a singular issue without actively enforcing the connection between them under the values of bioeconomy. By being active in this sector and through personal and working contacts, the BioINSouth Coordinator managed to acquire a substantial number of supportive stakeholders on a regional and national level, representing all types in the quadruple helix approach. The important collaboration with the Greek Bioeconomy Council is surely beneficial for the BioINSouth HUB. The BioINSouth HUB Coordinator has also expressed their intent to actively approach representatives of regional authorities, focusing on people that can actively assist on the interests of the BioINSouth HUB.

5.8 BioINSouth HUB of Slovenia

The Slovenian BioINSouth HUB, established before the start of the BioINSouth project by ACIS (Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Slovenia), operates under unique circumstances. It functions as an evolving stakeholder network focused on strengthening regional bioeconomy potential despite limited political support.

HUB members are actively engaged in several EU-funded projects— such as BIOLOC, RuralBioUp, CEE2ACT, BOOST4BIOEAST, and BioINSouth—ensuring continuous collaboration and policy relevance. To formalise this multi-project engagement, the HUB is introducing a joint Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) outlining member roles and responsibilities across the initiatives.

In place of a formal Kick-Off Meeting, the HUB will hold a Co-Creation Workshop in July 2025 to validate its Action Plan with stakeholders. This tailored approach reflects its mature structure and ongoing stakeholder involvement, reinforcing its commitment to long-term collaboration and impact.

As the BioINSouth Project progresses—and as its activities are sustained and expanded through the BioINSouth Initiative—the Slovenian HUB remains committed to fostering the active participation and engagement of its members and stakeholders.

6 Conclusion

D3.2 HUB guidelines has presented addressed some key points of the establishment and organisation of the BioINSouth HUBs, aiming to guide and assist the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators in decision making and managing of their BioINSouth HUBs. As of May 2025, the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators have established their HUBs by engaging their regional stakeholders and acquiring the signed MoUs from the representatives of the now member organisations. During the stakeholder engagement period, the BioINSouth HUB Coordinators realised the importance of establishing strong and meaningful

communication channels with their members, adapting to the types of relationships they can form with them based on their activities and expertise, and paying special attention to their stakeholders' needs and concerns. Their efforts will continue by constantly enhancing their outreach and communicating with more regional stakeholders and by solidifying their Members' involvement and trust in their BioINSouth HUB by presenting and validating with their assistance the regional BioINSouth HUB Action Plan, during the official Kick-Off Meeting of the HUB.

BioINSouth Info Box

The BioINSouth project aims to support decision-makers to incorporate considerations of ecological limits into their regional bioeconomy strategies and roadmaps relevant to circular bio-based activities. We aim to develop guidelines and digital tools, considering the safe and sustainable by design (SSbD) assessment framework, to support the adoption of innovative methodologies to assess environmental impacts in multiple industrial bio-based systems, increasing regional competitiveness and innovation capacity, and contributing to the EU fair & green transition.

Find out more:

Website: <https://www.bioinsouth.eu/>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/104361906/>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@BioINSouth>

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